

Market Orientation and Performance of Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria

Ndubuisi-Okolo Purity Uzoamaka, Ph.D

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Brewing firms in South-South, Nigeria has limitation in achieving market orientation due to persistent environmental challenges prevalent in today's contemporary and ever dynamic competitive environment. The incessant environmental challenges have influenced new product development, market share; innovation, caused unbalanced development and increased uncertainty. In view of the above, this work focused attention on market orientation and performance of brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, its set to determine the nature of relationship that exists between customer orientation and innovation in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria and nature of relationship that exists between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised of 120 staff of brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria which was reduced to 92 using Taro Yamane statistical formula for determining the Sample Size. Data generated from the copies of questionnaire administered to the respondent was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient which is an inferential statistical tool. The results of the analyses revealed that there is a statistical significant positive relationship between customer orientation and innovation and there is also a statistical significant positive relationship between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Based on the findings of this work, the investigator recommended that Brewing manufacturing firms need to embark on intensive customer and competitor orientation exercises since they serve as panaceas for increasing the quality of services that are being rendered to both the prospective and potential customers. This help to ensure that customers' needs are met and brewing firms stand the better chance of benefitting maximally.

Corresponding Author:
Ndubuisi-Okolo Purity
Uzoamaka

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INTRODUCTION

Market orientation portrays a business culture in which both employers and employees are expected to be seriously committed to the continuous creation of superior value for customers. It describes firm's strength that enables it to detect and respond positively to customers' needs in order to create and deliver superior value to them in terms of product quality and other associated variables. Superior value is achieved through creating acceptable standards and processes for customers via the collection and distribution of market information that will enable them to know the latest demands of the customers cum make timely, valuable and effective decisions. That is, the choices of the potential and prospective customers in order to attract and retain them since customer retention is a bane to numerous firms

coupled with market uncertainty (Fatonah & Haryanto 2022). Market orientation houses customer orientation, competitor orientation and inter-functional co-ordination. Customer orientation borders on generating adequate information about the potential and prospective customers that will enable the business to create superior value for them. It provides holistic knowledge on the latest trends in the market and equips the organization for full action in order to create superior value for existing and potential customers. Therefore, the hallmark of market orientation is to create superior value for customers since customers are kings without equivocation.

Firms are in existence to satisfy the needs of their customers, and as such, building innovation competencies

requires a strong set of organizational knowledge, understanding, skill sets, abilities, profundity, and motivations to ensure that innovation activities are targeted towards serving market needs and organizational goals (Olympic, 2014). To create value for customers, all units or departments in the organization must be involved to ensure that superior value is created and quality service is rendered to customers. Quality service being offered to customers leads to customer satisfaction, and when customers are satisfied, they can hardly leave the organization and customer retention becomes the order of the day. Market orientation provides the foundation of developing the organization's market-based capabilities which will facilitate the adoption and dissemination of generated information in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. To this achieve sustainable competitive advantage, there is need to understand the strengths, weaknesses, capabilities, and strategies of current and potential competitors in the market. This knowledge enables organizations to devise suitable strategies in order to outweigh their competitors and force them completely out of the market. Competitors are silenced via the adoption of diverse marketing strategies to quell their strengths. In view of the foregoing, some researchers like Davcik and Sharma, (2016) opine that market orientation leads to improved firm performance. Also, the study by Christina and Miloslava (2020) confirmed the relationship between market orientation and firm sustainable performance. Kropp et al. (2006) found that innovation, market orientation and organization learning strongly influence business performance. In the opinions of (Heirati and O’Cass, 2016), market orientation leads to new product innovation while (Kachouie, Mavondo & Sands, 2018) in their wealth of knowledge posited that market orientation leads to improved customer value and market effectiveness respectively. It is also obvious that in a highly volatile and competitive environment, firms that are market-oriented are both proactive and responsive to the needs of customers which will in turn give them edge over their competitors and increase firm performance. Therefore, there is always increase in firm performance and productivity when market orientation is strengthened owing to its ability to meet the changing needs of consumers at any point in the product development process (Christina & Miloslava 2020). It proves that concerted efforts need to be made by business players in enhancing their marketing activities. (Munck et al., 2020).

Brewing firms in South-South, Nigeria has limitation in achieving market orientation due to persistent environmental challenges prevalent in today’s contemporary and ever dynamic competitive environment. The incessant environmental challenges have influenced new product development, caused unbalanced development and increased uncertainty. In the light of the above, none of the studies reviewed to the best of my knowledge was able to establish

specifically a relationship between the components of market orientation (Customer orientation and competitor orientation) and indices of performance (innovation and quality service delivery) as articulated in this research. Also, a geographical gap is detected because market orientation has not been carried out in brewing firms in south-South, Nigeria based my research. These pitfalls form the lacuna which this empirical study intend to fill to quell the quagmire in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main thrust of this study is to determine the extent of relationship that exists between market orientation and performance of brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sets out to:

1. Determine the nature of relationship that exists between customer orientation and innovation in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria.
2. Examine the nature of relationship that exists between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

1. To what extent does customer orientation relates with innovation in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What is the nature of relationship that exists between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between customer orientation and innovation in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between competitor orientation and quality service quality in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria.

1.5 Significance of the study

Myriads of stakeholders will benefit significantly from this research work. It will serve as an eye-opener to organizations to be properly oriented on how to manage their potential and prospective customers in order to retain them permanently. Therefore, organizations will become more responsive to the yearnings of their customers since it is crystal clear that there are too many competitors in the market via the imperative of market orientation exposed in this work.

1.6 Scope of the study

This work dwells on market orientation and performance of Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria. The geographical scope is South-South, Nigeria comprising Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers State. The three brewing firms ranging from Champion

Brewery Plc (Akwa Ibom State); Guinness Nigeria Plc (Edo State); and Pabob Brewery Plc (Rivers State) were used for this study.

1.7 limitation of the study

The herculean aspect of the exercise was inability to illicit vital information from respondents. They were uncooperative and very secretive. However, the challenge was actually mitigated by persuasion and little application of wisdom.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Market Orientation

Market orientation is the act of gathering business-wide market intelligence of present and future customer needs, circulation of such information across all organizational departments, and it explains how the organization reacts either favourably or unfavourably to it. Market orientation is a business philosophy that dwells on eliciting timely, reliable and valuable information from customers and competitors and leveraging on synergy of shared efforts in generating value for customers and the firm (Julian, Mohamad and Sefnedi 2014). The above definition synchronizes with the definition of (Udriyah, et al., 2019) which stipulates that market orientation is a business philosophy that places a premium on identifying consumer needs and desires and meeting them through making products and services available to them at the right time and place. A paper written by Kumar, Jones, Venkatesan, and Leone (2011) confirmed that firms with positive market orientation record higher business performance than businesses with lower level of market orientation. Researchers in their submissions averred that market orientation is a key to a firm's success and enhances performance respectively (Jogaratham, 2017; Najafi-Tavani, Sharifi, & Najafi-Tavani, 2016). The sole aim of market orientation is to provide utility for customers as well as retain them. Essentially, a market oriented business organization shows itself as an open system which can exchange resources with its environment. Peter Drucker (1954) projected market orientation as a business philosophy which facilitates the idea that customers are kings and must be at the centre of management thinking and practices in order to ensure that they are satisfied via product availability and quality of service being rendered to them (Wishart, 2019). He declares that product availability is making sure that customers are not stranded at any point in time by ensuring that their demands are made available to them at the right time and at the right place. This depicts that businesses with higher degree of market orientation will exhibit better financial, economic, and positive management results. In view of the above, some scholars insist that firms need to pursue market orientation because it helps them gain long-term competitive advantage (Fakhreddin, et al., 2021; Hernández-Linares, et al., 2021; Alhakimi, & Mahmoud, 2020; Ho, et al., 2018). Studies conducted by (Lekmat, et al.,

2018; Sisay, et al., 2017; Joensuu-Salo, et al., 2018; and Chen, et al., 2015) opined that market orientation improves organizational performance.

2.1.1 Competitor Orientation

Competitors are unpredictable elements in a globally competitive and technologically-based environment. In tandem with this, an effective business strategy is needed to respond to competitors' movement. This is solely because the major aim of competitor orientation is to achieve continuous competitive advantage and to improve firms overall performance in terms of profitability, productivity, quality service delivery, customer satisfaction, increased market share etc. The overall performance is achieved under the auspices of orientation to customers, competitors and cross-functional coordination in the organization. (Yu et al, 2018).

2.1.1.1 Innovation

Innovation is a critical factor in management. It is a real indicator of performance in an organization. Eris and Ozmen (2012) aver that market orientation and innovation are the key strategies adopted by various organizations in order to achieve superior performance. The organization's ability to understand customer orientation leads to innovation. This is simply because when the needs and wants of the customers are known; the next line of action is: How to provide those needs of the customers in terms of improving the already existing products to suit them. Innovation comprises any kind of process, product, or practices in the organization that adds value towards sustainable development (Doran & Ryan, 2014). Innovation plays a pivotal role in ensuring that a business entity improves its performance in terms of customer satisfaction expectations which revolves around quality service delivery that leads to customer retention (Bylon, Jerry and Wright (2019)).

2.1.1.2 Quality service delivery

Customers' tastes are constantly changing due to dynamic, competitive and technologically-based environment. As a result, changes in customers' demands and wishes have also increased astronomically over the past decade (Ali, Hilman, and Gorondutse, 2020). Because of the changes in customers' tastes, it becomes imperative for organizations to consider the quality of services that will be rendered to customers based on their expectations and values. This is because customers are very crucial to the growth and survival of an organization. The quality of service offered to customers anchor on market orientation when informed decisions are made. Market orientation is the basis for quality service delivery as customers will only be satisfied if they perceive the service offered is a quality service (Bamfo, Dogbe and Osei-Wusu, 2018). Organizations must ensure that they offer high quality service if they want their customers to be satisfied and retained (Bamfo *et al.*, 2018). This implies that customer satisfaction depends on the quality of service rendered.

2.1.1.3 Theoretical Framework

This empirical work is anchored on resource-based theory, which ensures that the current internal resources and capability are active in affecting firm performance. This proposition is built on the model that an organization can do better than its competitors in the market by making effective and efficient use of its resources. Resources are the engine house of every business organization. The resources that are domicile in an organization determine its efficacy as regards providing superior value for customers as well as beating their competitors in the market. These resources include money, time, talent, energy, knowledge, skills, opportunities and capabilities. Also, customers will be adequately cared for when resources are judiciously utilized. Since organizational resources are scarce, efficient utilization of it will yield optimum result that will bring about superior value to customers.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Appiah-nimo and Chovancová (2020) studied improving firm sustainable performance: the role of market orientation. It analyzed the influence of market orientation on sustainable performance of firms, and provides an argument on the market orientation to sustainable performance relationship. This work reviewed literature obtained from several databases concerning the related fields. Literature search was conducted using the keywords search via Google scholar engine and other research databases including Scopus and Web of Science. The individual variables were used as key search terms, though a limited amount of information was found, literature on market orientation proved promising. Articles deemed relevant to this conceptual paper were retrieved and reviewed. The findings revealed that the relationship between market orientation and firm sustainable performance. Further, it assessed the mediating and moderating variables that impact the relationship between market orientation and firm sustainable performance. It is recommended that an empirical study need to be conducted to enhance the strength of the relationships.

Fatonah and Haryanto (2022) examined exploring market orientation, product innovation and competitive advantage to enhance the performance of SMEs under uncertain events in Indonesia.

The aim of this study is to build an empirical research model and establish the influence of market orientation on product innovation and competitive advantage. The study also showcases the intervening role of product innovation and competitive advantage on increasing market performance. In addition, market uncertainty is also tested in moderation in strengthening the relationship between product innovation and competitive advantage in market performance. The study tests 178 samples of Batik SME players in Surakarta. A purposive sampling was adopted as this research's sampling method. The result of this study shows empirically

that market orientation positively, significantly affects product innovation and competitive advantage. The test of mediation role between product innovation and competitive advantage in market performance also reveals positive and significant results. The result of the test on moderation role between Market uncertainty in the relationship between product innovation and competitive advantage on market performance also shows positive and significant influence on market performance.

Qiang, Xiande and Chris (2021) carried out research on customer orientation and innovation: A comparative study of manufacturing and service firms. The study aimed to determine the influence of customer orientation on innovation performance in manufacturing and service firms. A sample size of 1646 was used for the manufacturing firms while 686 was utilized for the service firms. The results proved that customer orientation positively affects service innovativeness and product innovativeness in manufacturing and service firms respectively, and that such effects are mediated by two crucial firm resources: supplier collaboration and technical capability. However, customer orientation has a stronger total effect on innovativeness and supplier collaboration has a stronger mediating effect on the relationship between customer orientation and innovativeness in service firms.

Olympic.C.Racela (2014) conducted a research on Customer Orientation, Innovation Competencies, and Firm Performance: A Proposed Conceptual Model. This work presents an interdisciplinary view combining literature from the fields of marketing, innovation, and organization studies and discusses the valuable role that a customer orientation may play in the development of innovation competencies and subsequent organizational outcomes. A customer orientation has often been criticized as constraining certain innovation processes. Nevertheless, since innovation is regarded as a knowledge-based capability, this paper posits that the execution of market-sensing, customer-relating and customer-response capabilities lend to, rather than inhibit, innovation competencies. In describing innovation, the view adopted here is on two distinct but interconnected concepts, namely creativity (i.e. idea generation and problem solving) and innovation (i.e. the implementation of creative ideas). A conceptual model, based on theoretical foundations from the dynamic capabilities perspective and resource advantage theory, is proposed connecting customer orientation, creativity, innovation and firm performance. Theoretical contributions, practical implications, and future research directions are also discussed.

Emmanuel A. Amangala, Andy Fred Wali(2020) researched on market orientation, Service quality perception, and customer satisfaction: The Role of Market-sensing Capabilities. The article examines the relationship between market orientation, customers' perception of firms' service quality (SQ), and their satisfaction in the Nigeria banking

sector. The Expectancy Confirmation Theory (ECT) was adopted. The population of this study comprised of employees and customers of Nigerian money deposit banks. Survey design was utilized using the quantitative paradigm. We employed simple random sampling technique to select employees and customers from each of the 21 banks making a total of 594 samples, and, thereafter, copies of questionnaire were distributed to customers and employees in the banking hall with the permission of banks. Simple linear and hierarchical regressions were used to test our formulated hypotheses and the study analysis revealed a positive significant relationship between market orientation and SQ perceptions of customers. Also, market orientation on customer satisfaction (CSAT) is found to be positive and significant. Market-sensing capabilities were found to have significant but weak effect on the relationship between market orientation and SQ perceptions. Market-sensing capabilities were found to have no effect on the relationship between market orientation and CSAT. In other words, market-sensing capabilities were found not to be a moderator of the relationship between market orientation and CSAT.

Bylon Abeeku Abamfor, Jerry Jay Kraa and Len Tiu Wright(2019) evaluated the impact of market orientation on performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana; the mediating role of innovation. The study was carried out on a total of 500 SMEs out of which 391 responses were received representing 78.2% response rate. Purposive and convenience sampling techniques were adopted in selecting the SMEs and structured questionnaire was used to collect data. Explanatory research design was used. The study used Structural Equation Model (SEM) for data analysis and explored various relationships as presented in the hypothesis. The findings indicated that, market orientation variable of customer orientation positively and significantly predict performance; while competitor orientation positively predicts performance; however, not significant. Inter-functional orientation inversely and non-significantly impacts on performance of SMEs in Ghana. Innovation partially mediates between customer orientation and performance. Innovation fully mediates between inter-functional orientations and performance whereas innovation has no mediation between competitor orientation and performance. Businesses, particularly SMEs are encouraged to adopt and embark on market orientation practices and implement innovative practices so as to achieve superior performance.

Jewel Dela Novixoxo1, Wisdom Wise Kwabla Pomegbe and Courage Simon Kofi Dogbe (2018) assessed market orientation, quality service, and customer satisfaction in public utility companies in Ghana. The study evaluated the adoption of market orientation construct in the public sector particularly the public utility companies and the linkage that exist between customer satisfaction, service delivery and market orientation. Survey research design was used to

generate data from 430 customers of the public utility companies in Ghana. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis and multiple regression. Results revealed a weak market orientation practiced by the utility companies. Consequently, customer's perception of service quality and satisfaction with the services with regards to the case company was affected. Market orientation concept has enjoyed tremendous review in the private sector compared to the public sector. This study is therefore adding to literature by extending the findings to the public sector where customer complaints abound. The findings of the study provide deep insights into handling customer issues in the public sector. The empirical evidence from this study provides strategic decisions that can be replicated to improve market orientation in the public sector, improve the way services are rendered and customer expectation of the services of the utility companies.

Moad Hamod M Saleh1*, Adi Anuar Azmin2, Ummi Naiemah Saraih (2021) determined the effect of market orientation, product innovation and marketing ethics on firm performance: A theoretical framework. This work established a theoretical link between market orientation and SME performance through a literature review. In addition, it developed a new framework for experimental evidence. This study made significant contributions to the understanding of the relationship between market orientation and SME performance but also sheds light on the critical role of product innovation as a mediator. Furthermore, the conceptual model explains the impact of marketing ethics as a moderator on small- and medium-sized enterprise (SMEs) performance.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design. The justification anchors on the nature of the study which utilizes structured questionnaire to elicit detailed information from the respondents. This research which focused attention on market orientation and performance of brewing firms in South-South, Nigeria has a total population of 120 reduced to 92 using Taro Yamane Formula for determining the sample size. Both validity and reliability test were conducted. The validity test revealed that the instrument was valid based on experts' opinions while the reliability test conducted proved a reliability value of 0.75 which was arrived at using test-re-test method. The result was considered reliable. Data gathered through questionnaire structured on five-point Likert scale were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. Findings found a statistically significant positive relationship between customer orientation and innovation and statistically significant positive relationship between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria.

4.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

There is a significant relationship between Customer orientation and innovation

Table 4.1.1: Correlation result on Customer orientation and innovation in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria.

Correlations

		CUSTOMER ORIENTATION	INNOVATION
CUSTOMER ORIENTATION	Pearson Correlation	1	.946**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	92	92
INNOVATION	Pearson Correlation	.946**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	92	92

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 4.1.1 displays the correlation result of customer orientation and innovation in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. From the table; it is shown that the correlation coefficient is .946 indicating that there is a positive significant relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. Also from the table, the p-value is .000. The level of significant used is (0.05). The result revealed that relationship observed from the analysis is statistically significant because the p-value is less than the level of significant used. This depicts that increase in customer orientation will tantamount to commensurate increase in innovation. This is because the more information is generated about customers; the more diverse strategies are adopted to improve their values. Therefore, we reject the

null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between customer orientation and innovation in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria ($r = .946, P < .05$). The finding of this study is in sync with research carried out by Bylon Abeeku Abamfor, Jerry Jay Kraa and Len Tiu Wright(2019) which averred that market orientation variable of customer orientation positively and significantly predict performance. It is also in tandem with the result of this study conducted by Fatonah and Haryanto (2022) which indicated empirically that market orientation (component of customer orientation) positively and significantly affects product innovation and competitive advantage.

Objective Two

To determine the nature of relationship that exists between competitor orientation and market share in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 4.1.2: Correlation Result on competitor orientation and quality service delivery in Brewing Manufacturing Firms in South-South, Nigeria.

Correlations

		COMPETITOR ORIENTATION	QUALITY SERVICE DELIVERY
COMPETITOR ORIENTATION	Pearson Correlation	1	.847**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	92	92
QUALITY SERVICE DELIVERY	Pearson Correlation	.847**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	92	92

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From table 4.1.2, the Pearson $r = .847$ tells us the type or nature of relationship existing between the study variables while the P-value tells us whether the result is statistically significant indicating whether to reject or accept either the

null or alternate hypothesis. The table shows that the correlation coefficient is .847 while the P-value is .000. Judging from the level of significance given, (0.05), the P-value (0.00) is less than the given level of significance which

signifies rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, I conclude that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between competitor orientation and quality service delivery in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria ($r = .847, P < 0.05$). This connotes that increase in competitor orientation leads to increase in quality service delivery and vice versa. This finding does not corroborate with the finding of Bylon Abeeku Abamfor, Jerry Jay Kraa and Len Tiu Wright (2019) which states that competitor orientation positively predicts performance; however, not significant. But the finding agrees with Bylon Abeeku Abamfor, Jerry Jay Kraa and Len Tiu Wright (2019) which categorically states that competitor orientation positively predicts performance.

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Market orientation is a key that unlocks dissemination of intelligent information that forms the basis for market growth, market share, quality service delivery, innovation and creativity in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. It is the actual practical implementation of creative ideas emanating from market orientation that leads to superior performance in all organizations. Superior performance revolves around market share, quality service delivery, innovation, etc. Based on the findings of this research, market orientation impacts positively on the performance of brewing manufacturing firms, from the responses of the respondents. This is further proven by indicating a significant positive relationship between customer orientation and quality service delivery and also portraying a positive significant relationship between competitor orientation and market share in brewing manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. Therefore, market orientation increases the level of performance in an organization if properly executed. As regards the findings of this work, the following recommendations are made:

1. Brewing manufacturing firms need to embark on intensive customer orientation exercise since it serves as a panacea for increasing the quality of services that are being rendered to both the prospective and potential customers. Be informed that when the needs of the customers are met, organizations stand the better chance of benefitting maximally.
2. Brewing manufacturing firms need to be more sensitive to the activities of their competitors in the market in order to achieve sustainability in all facets of their endeavours. This is because competitors are too powerful and have the capacity and profundity to force already existing firms out of market if their activities are not properly monitored and duly followed.

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